

Statistical Shape Analysis and Kansei Engineering

Unveiling complex relations between shapes and Kansei

Shigekazu Ishihara*, Keiko Ishihara*, Mitsuo Nagamachi*

**Dept. of Kansei Design, Hiroshima International University
555-36, Kurose-Gakuendai, Higashi-Hiroshima, Hiroshima, 739-2695, JAPAN
i-shige@he.hirokoku-u.ac.jp*

Abstract: Kansei Engineering is a method used to convert a customer's ambiguous images of products into a detailed design. *Kansei* is a Japanese word for feeling or impression. Kansei Engineering provides product designers a basis of design with associations between customers' feelings and corresponding concrete designs. Procedures consist of a psychological evaluation, multivariate analysis and various computer techniques such as 3D CG and VR. In this paper, we describe the method for focusing on product shapes concerning customers' Kansei, to avoid confusing effects on Kansei caused by other properties such as sizes, orientations, colors, textures, and so on. We standardized the shapes of sample products and made them into statistical values with morphometric methods. This preprocessing of the shape let us build mathematical models of shape space and relations between shapes and Kansei based on the results of customers Kansei evaluations. Then, statistical analyses that are frequently used in Kansei Engineering, e.g., cluster analysis and principal component analysis, followed to reveal the characteristics of shape samples associated with specific Kansei and semantic space of Kansei expressed for the products. Here, we described the proposed analysis method on headlights of passenger cars and present the resulting associations between concrete shapes and Kansei evaluation.

Key words: *Kansei Engineering, Shape Analysis, Morphometrics, Statistics, Geometry, Multivariate Analysis.*

1. Introduction

Kansei Engineering is a method to convert customers' ambiguous images of products into a detailed design to support designers by providing estimated evaluation of a design before throwing it into the market, and also to help customers choose what fits their feelings by showing them associated designs. Kansei Engineering was originated by Prof. Nagamachi about 30 years ago. Procedures consist of a psychological evaluation, multivariate analysis and various computer techniques such as 3D CG and VR. Kansei Engineering has been introduced in many world industries, such as automobile, electric home appliances, furniture and home products.

In this paper, we describe the method for focusing on product's shapes concerned with customers' Kansei, to avoid confusing effects on Kansei caused by other properties such as size, orientation, colors, textures, and so on. In Kansei Engineering, we have treated sample shapes as categorical variables in nominal scale. Examples of typical codings are, e.g. 'long' or 'tall/short, cubic', 'round/square corners'. Relations between Kansei evaluation and categories of design elements have often been analyzed by using Quantification Theory Type I. The relations

between them are represented as a multivariate regression model assigning categorical design elements to explanatory variables (Xs) and Kansei evaluation value to an objective variable (Y). The problem is to solve each weight of X to find what design elements contribute to strengthen a specific Kansei. This mode of analysis is useful in practical applications where the product has compounds of various types of design elements. Shapes had not been treated as mathematical quantity for a long time in Kansei studies.

The categorical coding of design elements, however, falls short of dealing with the details of designs in the analysis, although many design elements should be expressed in analog continuous figures in an interval scale with proper measurement. If we deal with shapes as continuous values, shapes can be analyzed with various statistical techniques such as distribution type consideration, model building with regression, classification and projection onto a lower dimensional space. Then, we can build mathematical models of shape space and relations between shapes and Kansei.

In this study, we propose to use methodologies of morphometrics to convert shapes into statistically treatable values, so that we may seek the relations concerning Kansei. Morphometrics have been developed in paleontology to statistically analyze shapes of fossilized ancient beings. Because most fossil samples are found with different age in different places, their sizes often differ. In addition, fossils do not have standard horizontal or vertical basis lines or planes. Therefore, when comparing shape variations of fossils, they have to be aligned and rotated to minimize the directional differences. These processes are also needed in a case of Kansei analysis.

We analyzed associations between the shapes of the car headlights and Kansei. Although the design of the headlights was a composite of various elements, we focused on how the variation of shape solely affected the participants' Kansei evaluations. By using results of statistical analyses, we can specify how to change the shape numerically to strengthen a specific Kansei. We describe a method of analysis where we put morphometrics methodology into Kansei analysis in the case of car headlights.

2. Methodology of Morphometrics

In morphometrics, a shape is represented as coordinates by morphological or functional landmarks.

2.1. Comparison between shapes

The problems we encounter were quite similar to that of paleontology. The size of a headlight varied between cars. Many lights were differently oblique; some lights were upward and others were horizontal. The raw data of the shapes of the left headlight that were obtained from the measurement of real cars are shown in Figure 1. The shapes of twenty-seven headlights are drawn with the lower left corner assigned to an anchor point in the figure.

We had three problems in comparing the shapes: (1) Which point (landmark) to choose as an anchor. When we choose a landmark as an anchor, the distribution of the anchor among all shapes becomes very small, however, other landmarks are widely distributed, as we see how the landmarks in the right end of the lights are largely distributed in Figure 1. Multivariate analyses cannot be applied to such data with largely different distribution. The other problems were: (2) Orientations of shapes were different and (3) Sizes were also different. We had to standardize both orientations and sizes to compare the shapes and convert them into statistical variables.

Figure 1. Raw data plots of measured headlights.

2.2. Procedure of the morphometrics

The flow of the morphometrics procedures is shown in Figure 2. At first, we align all shapes by an anchor point. We adopted the idea of “centroid size” [1] to make an anchor point and standardize the size. The centroid of a shape was calculated and assigned to an anchor point. The centroid size is the sum of the squared distance from the centroid to each landmark. The size of a shape was standardized by centroid size. Then, we rotated the shapes and made them share the same orientation by using the “Generalized Procrustes (GP) method” [2]. GP minimize the sum of squared distances between corresponding landmarks of two samples. Therefore, we treated the landmark coordinates as multi-dimensional normal-distributed values.

Although computing procedures are not particularly complicated as optimization methods, geometrical and statistical theory of GP to treat landmarks were given during 1994 to 1998 (refer [2]). Thus, the theoretical basis of morphometrics is established in very recent years.

Figure 2. Morphometrics procedure and correspondent spaces.

Here, we show the GP algorithm and its geometry with practical examples. We combined mathematical concepts which were provided by Dryden & Mardia [2], Minaka [3] and Zelditch [4].

Figure Space: The first space is called “figure space,” in which the measured landmark data are represented. The datum in the figure space places k landmarks in the m dimensional space. In our example, there are 2 triangles \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} , those are drawn in a 2-dimensional plane. (Figure 2(a)). \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} are matrices those correspond to each triangles. They have 3 landmarks in the 2-dimensional plane, then 3 rows and 2 columns matrices ($k=3, m=2$).

$$\mathbf{V} = \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 3 \\ 12 & 22 \\ 33 & 8 \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{W} = \begin{bmatrix} 29 & 16 \\ 35 & 30 \\ 53 & 14 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Pre-form Space: A space contains landmark coordinates of shapes; those had been aligned with their centroid positions. The centroid of a shape on 2-dimensional space is the average of k coordinates on each axis. It is shown as a vector \mathbf{c} , which has c_1 on x axis and c_2 on y axis.

$$\mathbf{c} = (c_1, c_2) \quad \mathbf{c}_j = \frac{1}{k} \sum_{i=1}^k \mathbf{X}_{ij} \quad (2)$$

In this example, $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{v})$, the centroid of triangle \mathbf{V} is (16, 11) and $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{w})$ is (39, 20). Then the landmark coordinates of \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} in pre-form space are,

$$\mathbf{V}_{\text{centered}} = \mathbf{V} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{v}) \\ \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{v}) \\ \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{v}) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -13 & -8 \\ -4 & 11 \\ 17 & -3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{W}_{\text{centered}} = \mathbf{W} - \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{w}) \\ \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{w}) \\ \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{w}) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -10 & -4 \\ -4 & 10 \\ 14 & -6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Since the centroid is the average of landmark coordinates, then subtracting the centroid from landmark coordinates creates a new centroid of a shape as (0, 0). Then, at a triangle, when 2 landmark coordinates were given, one last landmark will fixed. For the number of the required space dimension, a triangle can be identified with 2 landmark coordinates in 2-dimensional space, that is, $km-m = 4$ dimensional space.

Pre-shape space: Standardization of the shape sizes by centroid size, creates a pre-shape space. Centroid size s is defined with eq (4).

$$s(\mathbf{x}) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{j=1}^m (\mathbf{X}_{ij} - \mathbf{c}_j)^2} \quad (4)$$

$\mathbf{V}_{\text{centered}}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{\text{centered}}$ have these values, since their centroids have already become (0,0).

$$s(\mathbf{V}_{\text{centered}}) = \sqrt{(-13)^2 + (-8)^2 + (-4)^2 + 11^2 + 17^2 + (-3)^2} = 2\sqrt{167} = 25.8457$$

$$s(\mathbf{W}_{\text{centered}}) = \sqrt{(-10)^2 + (-4)^2 + (-4)^2 + 10^2 + 14^2 + (-6)^2} = 4\sqrt{29} = 21.5407 \quad (5)$$

Then, landmark coordinates of two triangles in pre-shape space are obtained by dividing each centroid size (Figure 2(c)).

$$\mathbf{V}_{\text{pre_shape}} = \left(\frac{1}{s(\mathbf{V}_{\text{centered}})} \right) \mathbf{V}_{\text{centered}} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.5030 & -0.3095 \\ -0.1548 & 0.4256 \\ 0.6577 & -0.1161 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{W}_{\text{pre_shape}} = \left(\frac{1}{s(\mathbf{W}_{\text{centered}})} \right) \mathbf{W}_{\text{centered}} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.4642 & -0.1857 \\ -0.1857 & 0.4642 \\ 0.6499 & -0.2785 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Since the sizes of the triangles were standardized, then the sum of the distances from the centroid to the 3 landmarks is 1. Then, each triangle can be shown as a dot on the pre-shape sphere in 4-dimensional space.

In papers of morphometrics methodologies, a landmark coordinate is often expressed as a dot on the complex plane, to express (x,y) bi-variate coordinates as one value. Then, the pre-shape sphere of triangles becomes the sphere in 3-dimensional space. This is convenient for making concrete image.

Shape space: Manipulation of direction alignment of size-standardized triangles creates the “shape space”. The landmark matrix has (x,y) coordinates of a landmark at each row. In this example, $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$ is the reference and $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape}$ will be aligned by rotation. Rotation of the landmark matrix and the rotated $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape}$ are written as eq. (7).

$$\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \\ e & f \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \cos[\Theta] & -\sin[\Theta] \\ \sin[\Theta] & \cos[\Theta] \end{bmatrix}^T = \begin{bmatrix} a\cos[\Theta] - b\sin[\Theta] & a\sin[\Theta] + b\cos[\Theta] \\ c\cos[\Theta] - d\sin[\Theta] & c\sin[\Theta] + d\cos[\Theta] \\ e\cos[\Theta] - f\sin[\Theta] & e\sin[\Theta] + f\cos[\Theta] \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape,rotated} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.4642\cos[\Theta] + 0.1857\sin[\Theta] & -0.4642\sin[\Theta] - 0.1857\cos[\Theta] \\ -0.1857\cos[\Theta] - 0.4642\sin[\Theta] & -0.1857\sin[\Theta] + 0.4642\cos[\Theta] \\ 0.6499\cos[\Theta] + 0.2785\sin[\Theta] & 0.6499\sin[\Theta] - 0.2785\cos[\Theta] \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

θ in eq.(7) should be decided to minimize the difference between $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape,rotated}$. This means that it minimizes the distance d between the corresponding landmarks of two shapes. When there are two matrices \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{H} , both of them have 3 rows and 2 columns, $d(\mathbf{G},\mathbf{H})$ is defined by eq.(8). $d(\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}, \mathbf{W}_{pre-shape})$ is 0.2139.

$$d(\mathbf{G},\mathbf{H}) = \sqrt{(g_{11} - h_{11})^2 + (g_{12} - h_{12})^2 + \dots + (g_{31} - h_{31})^2 + (g_{32} - h_{32})^2} \quad (8)$$

This rotation alignment procedure is shown in Figure 3. A pre-shape triangle is shown as a dot on a 4-dimensional sphere. In Figure 3, $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape,rotated}$ is becoming close to fixed $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$, by rotation.

Figure 3. Alignment by rotation shown on Pre-shape sphere

In this example, we minimized $d(\mathbf{V},\mathbf{W})$ by rotation with Simplex method optimization computation. As the result of optimization, θ was obtained as 0.1532(radian)[8.7778 (degree)]. By applying θ to eq.7, finally we get this coordinate matrix.

$$\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape,rotated} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.4305 & -0.2544 \\ -0.2544 & 0.4305 \\ 0.6848 & -0.1761 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Shape Distances: As we have shown in Figure 3, the distance between size-standardized and direction-aligned triangles \mathbf{V} and \mathbf{W} is the “shape” difference. This distance avoids difference of both size and direction. There are three variations of the orientation; Procrustes Distance, Partial Procrustes Distance and Full Procrustes Distance.

Partial procrustes distance corresponds to the distance of tunneling inside the sphere that is the shortest pass. This is the squared distance between corresponding landmarks of $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape, rotated}$, and obtained with the same computation as eq.(8). $dp(\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}, \mathbf{W}_{pre-shape, rotated})$, the partial procrustes distance between $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape, rotated}$ is 0.1503.

Procrustes distance is the distance on the unit sphere, then called geodesic distance by analogy to surveying on the earth. Since the sphere is the unit sphere, the distance between two points is equal to ρ , an angle from the origin. The angle ρ is obtained by $\rho = 2 \arcsin(dp/2)$. In this example, ρ between $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$ and $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape, rotated}$ is 0.1504 radian (8.618 degree).

Full procrustes distance is the distance between B and $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$. B is the cross point of a line from the center to $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape, rotated}$ and a perpendicular line from it to $\mathbf{V}_{pre-shape}$. Since the distance from the origin to the surface is 1, then the magnification of \mathbf{W} at B is $\cos(\rho)$. In this example, magnification is $\cos(0.1504) = 0.9887$, then the resulting shape is a slightly reduced size of $\mathbf{W}_{pre-shape, rotated}$. This shape is called “Kendall’s Shape”.

$$\mathbf{W}_{Kendall'sShape} = \cos(\rho) \mathbf{W}_{pre-shape, rotated} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.4256 & -0.2515 \\ -0.2515 & 0.4256 \\ 0.6771 & -0.1741 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

In this example, we used \mathbf{V} as a reference of alignment. When we compare three or more shapes, the common method is set an average shape between all samples. The procedure is 1. One sample (i.e., the first sample) is set as a tentative average shape 2. Compute an average shape between all aligned samples 3. Then, the averaged shape is set as a reference and alignment is done again 4. A new averaged shape is computed again, and if it is not so differed from previous average shape, the process is ended; otherwise, return to 3. Usually, two or three iterations are enough for convergence [9].

Figure 4. Concept of three different distances (on a section of Pre-shape sphere)

Projection from Kendall’s Shape Space to Tangent Plane: The shape space made from point B is called “Kendall’s Shape Space”. As shown on Figure 5, the radius of the Pre-shape sphere becomes the diameter of Kendall’s Shape Space.

Since Pre-shape sphere and Kendall’s Shape Space are the sphere, thus applying linear analyses on distances between dots having difficulties. Then, the tangent space (tangent plane) should be considered, which attaches to

the point of the reference shape as a pole of the sphere. In this example, the reference point $V_{pre-shape}$ is the pole and when there are three or more shapes, the average shape is the reference and it becomes the pole.

Since the tangent space is a Euclid space, thus a projection onto it enables applying many multivariate analysis techniques. The projected coordinates are called ‘‘Tangent Coordinates’’.

There are three alternatives of the method of projection. In Figure 5, C is the enlongment of the line from the origin to A. The distance between the reference point and C is larger than the corresponding Procrustes distance. Also it can grow larger to infinite, when ρ is larger.

Point E is a perpendicular projection of point B, which shows the Full Procrustes Distance. The distance between the reference point and B is the smallest among other distances. Maximum distance is equal to the radius of Kendall’s Shape Space.

Point D is a perpendicular projection of point A, which shows the Partial Procrustes Distance. Dryden and Mardia ([2] pp.76) wrote that the difference of D and E is very small, and both of them are applicable in most practical cases. In a later part of this paper, we used Full Procrustes Distance (point E) for the analysis.

Figure 5. Variations of projection method for tangent space

3. Kansei evaluation of morphometrically treated shapes of headlights

We show that it is useful for statistical analysis of relationships between design elements and Kansei to morphometrically treat the product shapes. Then, we also show results of multivariate techniques [5,6] to analyze associations between shapes and Kansei. We conducted a Kansei evaluation experiment on 27 passenger car headlights.

3.1. Morphometric treatment of headlights as evaluation stimuli for Kansei evaluation

Headlight shapes are measured from the photographs of 27 Japanese and European sedans and mini-vans. Each photo was taken at 1m distant from the left headlight.

The coordinates of each light were measured by superimposing mesh on the photo. Morphological landmarks (maximum curvature points) and functional landmarks (at the boundary between direction indicator part) are marked in the front face. We took eight landmarks, left end of the light, max curvature points on the upper and lower lines toward the left end, upper and lower boundaries between the light and the direction indicator, max curvature points on the upper and lower lines toward the direction indicator, and right end of the light.

Figure 6. Measurement of headlight and the shape composed of 8 landmarks (Mazda Axela)

Twenty-seven measured landmark shapes were standardized on size and orientation with generalized procrustes analysis (GPA) described above. We used the “Shapes” package written by Dryden and Mardia (1998) for GPA computation, which runs on an R statistical analysis environment. The Shapes package can be downloaded from CRAN, the repository of R project.

Figure 7. Upper left to right; Measured data, GPA alignment, a sample after GPA, and a stimulus for Kansei evaluation

A total of twenty-eight GPA treated shapes, 27 and the average shape, were used as evaluation stimuli. Each shape of headlight was a line drawing of 8 connected landmarks. We added the same drawing of a bumper and a bonnet (hood) to avoid influence of car differences.

Participants were 13 males (12 persons of 20-23 years old and one 41 years old). They rated the stimuli on 58 Kansei words with a 5-point SD scale on the questionnaire.

4. Statistical analyses of associations between shapes and Kansei evaluation

4.1. Classification of shapes and association to Kansei evaluation

Cluster analysis on 28 shapes of the lights was performed. The shape data were 16-dimensional, 8 landmarks by 2 dimensions. Clustering was done with Euclid distance and UPGMA. We decided on an 8-cluster solution due to the distance change. The dendrogram is shown in Figure 8.

Kansei evaluation values were averaged for the shapes that were belong to each cluster. Averaged Kansei words that rated higher than the total mean evaluation value + 1SD, 3.52, were regarded as features on the cluster.

On the left-hand side of Figure 8, cluster 2, including samples 2, 20, 21, ..., 13 was highly evaluated on “slim,” “simple,” “adult” and “sporty”. Samples belonging to cluster 2 were thin and had cusp inner (left) corners. Cluster 3 included samples 7, 28, ..., 25 and the mean shape 28 had no highly evaluated words. Samples classified into cluster 3 had middle height and narrow cusp on the left corner. Samples belong to cluster 4 (12, 17, ... 16) have hexagonal shape and highly evaluated on “masculine”. Samples in cluster 6 (on the right-hand side

of the figure, including samples 5, 10 and 6) were wedge shaped and were highly evaluated on “futuristic”, “young”, “casual” and “bright”.

The associations between major shape variation and Kansei were identified by this cluster analysis on shape.

Figure 8. Results of cluster analysis on shapes.

4.2 Principal component analysis of shapes and analysis on Kansei space

Next, we performed principal component analysis of shapes. Principal component analysis (PCA) of shapes finds projections of shapes distributed in higher dimensional space onto the lower dimensional space. In this case, headlights were expressed in 8 landmarks by 2 dimensional data, thus their shapes were distributed in 16-dimensional space, which was hard to understand. We used PCA as a useful tool to consider the shape variation concerning tendencies on Kansei.

Three major principal components (PCs) were identified with PCA. They explained 77.9% of total variations. Figure 9 shows the principal component scores of shapes along the PCs.

In Figure 10, we plot the coordinates of landmarks those correspond to; $-3SD$, mean and $+3SD$ in theoretical values along each PC. The first PC is on the top row, the second PC is on the middle and the third PC is on the bottom row. The shapes were rotated by -51 degree in the alignment optimization. Deformation grids obtained from the Thin Plate Spline (TPS) method [1] are shown in the rightmost column in the figure. These grids show changes of shapes from the mean shape to that with $+3SD$.

The first PC showed the variation of thickness, and it roughly corresponded to affine transformation (linear global deformation). Thicker samples were highly evaluated on “unique”, “powerful” and “massive”. On the other hand, thinner samples were highly rated on “slim”, “sporty” and “simple”. The second PC showed the difference (cusp or no cusp) on the inner, left corner and it corresponded to non-affine transformation (local deformation). Along the negative direction (cusp), “slim” and “sharp” had high scores, meanwhile, along the positive direction (no cusp), “young” and “sporty” were highly rated. The third PC showed the mutation from wedge to box shape and also corresponded to local deformation. The curvature of left corner changed and the

maximum curvature point of the right corner was also moved along the PC. Wedges were highly evaluated on “futuristic”, “urbanized”. Boxes were highly evaluated on “powerful” and “massive”.

From the results of shape principal component analysis, relations between a shape and its space are revealed. We could also decompose variations of light design into major design components: thickness, cusp of corners and wedge-boxy shape.

Figure 9. Shape variation along 3 PCs. (above), $-3SD/mean/+3SD$ theoretical value and deformation grid by TPS

4.3 Analysis on space composed by shapes and Kansei with local regression method

Finally, we investigated the shapes in Kansei evaluation space.

Relations between shape space and Kansei are often not linear, because Kansei responds to both the total feature (e.g., thickness) and local details (e.g., “eye tail”), that we considered. Therefore, we use a non-linear model to capture local relations between shape variation and Kansei. We devised a graphical analysis method on shape and Kansei space with a “local regression” method.

A common regression method fits a single regression model to the entire data. In the equation below, X_i is each observation of independent variable and Y_i is each observation of dependent variable. a is the regression coefficient, b is the bias and e is the error or residuals [7].

$$(\text{minimize})\epsilon = \sum_{i=1}^n (ax_i + b - y_i)^2 \quad (11)$$

Different from regression models in common use, the local linear regression model (LLR) is a model of one of non-parametric regression methods. In many cases, LLR fits a regression equation to a single Y observation that corresponds to the X_i . LLR uses X_i and n neighboring data X_s ($n_{local} X$) around the X_i , as independent variables (Eq.12). This procedure is called local fitting. w_{ij} is the kernel function, and used as a local weight parameter function. Single-peak functions are often used for w_{ij} and it decays as distance increases [7].

$$(\text{minimize})\epsilon(x_j) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{local}} w_{ij} (a_j x_i + b_j - y_i)^2 \quad (12)$$

Local regression (LOESS) method uses a local part of the data; then, it is useful for data smoothing. We used LOESS method proposed by Cleveland et al. [8]. Their LOESS uses cubic function as a kernel function.

In figure 10, we show a mapping of PC scores and smoothed Kansei evaluation value on “contemporary” (*span*; kernel function range was set as 0.5. PC scores were multiplied by 100).

Figure 10. “Contemporary” evaluation map on shape PC score

Highly evaluated region was in the L-shape lies from upper left to lower middle of the graph. Thin lights, or lights with cusp inner eye-end and round outer eye-end were highly evaluated (such shapes are shown with a solid outgoing line from the graph). Lowly evaluated region lies in the center of the graph. Their shapes were thick squared (such shapes are pointed by dashed outgoing line).

It is useful to combine the shape PCA and smoothed evaluation value mapping for revealing such non-linear relations and interactions between design elements. For example, “adult” had high scores on the shapes that lie from the upper left to the lower middle. There was a “valley” on the lower right. Thin lights were highly rated;

the relations were almost linear. On “refined”, only the shapes in the lower left corner were highly rated. They had a cusp inner eye corner. It was found that particular design elements had non-linear effects on specific Kansei.

Figure 11. “Adult” (left) and “refined” (right) evaluation map on shape PC score

4. Conclusions

We developed a new method to statistically analyze associations between shapes and Kansei by applying the methods of morphometrics and local regression. Statistical analysis of shapes is the very first attempt in Kansei Engineering field. Our proposed method is useful in practical application of Kansei Engineering in industries; it gives decomposition of complicated shapes of products into major design components, so that the product shape can be directly determined with detailed shape and size. This method is further developed; we recently utilized morphometrics applied to facial cognition [9,10] and to automatically generate landmarks on 3D objects [11].

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